

THE STRENGTH AND ELASTIC MODULUS OF MULTIFILAMENT SiC FIBRES

C.H. ANDERSSON and R. WARREN

*Department of Engineering Metals
Chalmers University of Technology - Gothenburg, Sweden*

The tensile strength and Young's modulus has been investigated of multifilament SiC fibres produced from a polymer precursor. The strength variations of the fibres with respect to length could be described satisfactorily in terms of Weibull statistics though this was complicated by the relatively wide distribution of fibre diameters. The mean strength of the fibre was given by the equation:

$$\ln \bar{\sigma} = 8.12 - 0.128 \ln L$$

with $\bar{\sigma}$ in MPa and the fibre length, L , in mm. Heat treatment of the fibres in hydrogen above 1000°C caused a reduction of the Weibull modulus and decreases in strength. The average Young's modulus of the fibres was found to be 200 ± 10 GPa after correction for end errors in the fibre testing arrangement. Defects, sometimes causing fracture initiation, were observed on the fibre surfaces.

INTRODUCTION

In 1975, Yajima reported the successful development on a laboratory scale of multifilament SiC fibres produced by the pyrolysis of a Si-bearing polymer [1,2]. The production of the fibres has subsequently been developed to a commercial pilot level. The structure and properties of the fibres have been investigated extensively by Yajima and co-workers [3,4]. They possess a β -SiC crystalline structure of very fine, randomly oriented crystallites. Yajima reports the existence of a significant proportion of SiO₂ and free carbon in the fibres which would be a possible explanation of their relatively low density of 2.6 gcm⁻³ (cf. 3.2 gcm⁻³ for normal SiC).

The fibres have high strength, a relatively high Young's modulus and excellent oxidation resistance. These properties are retained to at least 1000°C and the fibres hold therefore considerable promise as a reinforcement for elevated temperature use. In this laboratory, the incorporation of the fibres in metal matrix composites is being investigated. The present work, forming a part of this investigation, is a study of the mechanical and elastic properties of the fibres. Special emphasis has been placed on the effect of fibre length. Recently, Hitchon and Phillips, in a study of C-fibres, demonstrated how the effects of fibre length on strength can be described in terms of Weibull statistics [5]. This approach is also used here.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material

The investigated fibres, received in 1977, were taken at an early stage of the development of the pilot commercial production and are thus not necessarily representative of current production. Samples for testing were taken at random from a batch weighing about 250 g. The following fibre properties were quoted by the supplier: diameter 12.3 μ m; UTS 2520 MPa; Young's modulus 142 GPa.

The fibres possessed a bluish surface film, presumed to be oxide, that could be removed by dissolution in hydrofluoric acid or an aqueous NaOH solution. Such treatment resulted in a 2-5 % loss in weight which corresponds to a film thickness of about 0.1 micron.

Powdered samples were examined with a Philips X-ray diffractometer and found to have a β -SiC crystal structure and, using the Scherrer analysis [6], an effective crystallite size of 1.3 nm. The average diameter (of 114 fibres) was found to be 11.95 microns but the diameter varied considerably between individuals as is shown in the next section.

Procedure

The strength and Young's modulus of individual fibres was measured using a table model Instron testing machine with a 100 g load cell and pneumatic grips. The fibres were mounted for testing as illustrated in Fig. 1. The ends of the fibre were fixed with drops of epoxy resin adhesive to two L-shaped pieces of card held together by a spring clip. The specimens could be carried in this way to the testing machine. Once the two pieces of card were held in the machine grips the clip could be removed and the tensile test performed. After testing, the fibre diameter was measured using a Reichert microhardness micrometer. Where possible the diameter was measured at the point of fracture but in most cases it was found necessary to measure on part of the fibre on the other side of the adhesive. In a separate investigation it was found that the variation of the diameter along individual fibres (10-20 cm long) was seldom greater than the uncertainty involved in the micrometer measurement (approx. \pm 0.25 micron) but could sometimes reach about \pm 0.5 micron.

Fibre samples were tested with test lengths: 2, 5, 10, 44, 50, 88, 176 and 264 mm. Each sample consisted of between 10 and 20 individual fibre tests. For lengths 2, 5, 10, 44 and 50 mm, a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm per min. was used. The series, 44, 88, 176 and 264 mm was chosen to obtain the same strain rate (1.89×10^{-4} s⁻¹) with the various crosshead speeds of the testing machine. This series was chosen

Fig. 1. Fibre mounted for tensile testing.

for the measurement of apparent Young's modulus, relying on the coupling between crosshead and chart recorder movements for the measurement of strain.

A series of samples was also tested after 1 or 2 h heat-treatments in hydrogen at temperatures of 1000, 1225 and 1300°C.

The surface of the as-received fibres and in some cases the fracture surfaces of tested fibres were examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). A polished metallographic cross-section through a composite of the fibres in an iron matrix, prepared by hot isostatic pressing at 950°C, was also examined.

RESULTS

Fibre diameter

The distribution of the diameters of 114 tested fibres is shown in Fig. 2. The variation, being from about 8 to 20 micron, is large compared to that observed, e.g., in C-fibres. The variation is also revealed in the Fe-matrix composite shown in Fig. 3. The average diameter of the fibres in Fig. 2 was 11.95 micron; the majority lay within the limits of 10 to 13 microns.

Fibre strength

The basis of Weibull statistics is an empirical equation assumed to predict the probability of survival, P_S , of a specimen as a function of its volume, V , and the applied stress σ :

$$P_S = \exp \left[-V \left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_u}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right] \quad (1)$$

where σ_u is the stress below which fracture never occurs (often assumed to be 0) and σ_0 is a constant for the given material. m is the Weibull modulus; it is a measure of the variation of the failure probability and is related to the spatial and size distributions of the flaws that lead to failure. On taking logarithms and assuming $\sigma_u = 0$, Eq. (1) becomes:

$$\ln \ln (1/P_S) = \ln V + m \ln \sigma - m \ln \sigma_0 \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. Distribution of tested fibre diameters.

Fig. 3. Section through Fe-SiC fibre composite.

For specimens in which the flaws are confined to the surface, V can be replaced by S , the surface area. In a series of fibres of the same length, L , and the same diameter this equation implies that a plot of $\ln \ln (1/P_S)$ against $\ln \sigma_f$ (where σ_f is the fibre fracture stress) should yield a straight line of slope m . Here P_S can be defined as $n/(N+1)$ where n is the number of fibres surviving the stated stress σ_f and N the total sample number. The mean fibre strength, $\bar{\sigma}$, is that value corresponding to $P_S = 0.5$. For a series of samples of different lengths but the same diameter Eq. (2) predicts the following dependence of sample mean strength on sample length:

$$\ln \bar{\sigma} = - (1/m) \ln L - 0.367/m + \log \sigma_0 \quad (3)$$

Thus if the Weibull treatment is applicable, the strength for any fibre length can be predicted from measurements made on one or two lengths only.

Fibre strength distributions for three of the sample lengths are shown in Fig. 4 while in Fig. 5 four of the samples are plotted on Weibull co-ordinates. The latter exhibit reasonable agreement with the prediction of straight lines, though in some samples (e.g. $L = 88$ mm) the occurrence of a few weak fibres caused deviation. The results for all the fibre samples expressed as the Weibull parameters $\bar{\sigma}$ and m are summarized in Table 1. The values of m were obtained using a least squares analysis, omitting obviously deviant points such as those in parenthesis in Fig. 5.

With the exception of the 2 mm sample the Weibull moduli of all the samples lie relatively close to 4. Similar values were reported for C-fibres by Hitchon and Phillips [5]. The expected increase in average strength with decreasing length is observed and is illustrated as a plot of $\ln \bar{\sigma}$ vs $\ln L$ in Fig. 6. The straight line giving a least squares fit in this figure is given by the equation:

$$\ln \bar{\sigma} = 8.12 - (1/7.8) \ln L \quad (4)$$

with $\bar{\sigma}$ in N/mm^2 and L in mm. Thus, the value of m is here somewhat higher than is suggested by the sample plots of Fig. 5. Possible reasons for this are discussed in the next section.

Fig. 4. Strength distributions of three SiC fibre samples of different lengths.

Fig. 5. Weibull plots of four different SiC fibre samples.

Sample length L (mm)	Sample number N	Mean diameter (micron)	Strain rate (s ⁻¹) x 10 ⁴	Mean strength $\bar{\sigma}$ (MPa)	Weibull modulus m
264	10	11.5	1.89	1680	4.87
176	17	11.8	1.89	1670	3.74
88	18	11.4	1.89	2005	4.38
50	10	12.4	1.67	1700	3.77
45.4*	17	11.1	1.84	2340	4.24
10	15	12.9	8.33	2560	5.27
5	10	12.2	16.67	2930	3.84
2	22	12.6	41.67	2905	8.22

* nominal length, 44 mm.

Table 1. Summary of fibre tensile tests as function of sample length.

Fig. 6. The effect of fibre length on the mean fibre strength plotted as $\ln \bar{\sigma}$ and $\ln L$.

Heat Treatment

The strength testing of heat treated fibres is summarised in Table 2 and the effect of heat treatment temperature on the retained strength of the fibres is illustrated in Fig. 7. A significant reduction of strength began above about 1000°C. This was accompanied by a fall in the Weibull modulus which, in terms of a Weibull interpretation, implies the creation of new defects in the fibres. The fibres treated at 1225 and 1300°C could only be tested with short fibre lengths and the strength values in Fig. 7 have been adjusted to a value of $L = 50$ mm using the appropriate m values.

X-ray diffraction measurements on the powdered samples indicated an increase in the SiC crystallite size with heat treatment (Table 2). Further studies are required, however, to determine the relative importance of such structural effects and, e.g., the effect of surface attack by the environment.

Heat treatment temp (°C); time (h)	L (mm)	Sample size, N	$\bar{\sigma}$ (MPa)	m	$\bar{\sigma}$ (L=50 mm) (MPa)	Crystal size (nm)	
as-received	50	--	2050	4	2050	1.3	
1000;	2	50	9	1740	3.3	1740	---
1225;	1	24	10	1160	2.34	850	2.0
1300;	1	10	7	825	2.29	405	2.3

Table 2. Details of the tensile testing of heat-treated fibres.

Fig. 7. Effect of heat treatment (1-2h) on fibre strength.

Young's modulus

The load-extension curves of the fibres showed no significant deviation from linearity. The apparent, mean Young's moduli, E' , of the fibre samples, calculated directly from the recorded stress and strain at fracture, are shown in Table 3.

Sample length (mm)	45.4	50	88	176	264
Young's modulus (GPa)	168	152	184	186	189

Table 3. Apparent Young's modulus of tested fibres.

The modulus clearly tends to increase with sample length and this can be attributed to end errors such as load-related strain in the adhesive holding the fibre ends and in the load cell [7]. These errors can be circumvented by extrapolation to infinitely long samples in a plot of $1/E'$ vs. $1/L$ as shown by Mehan [7]. The above results are presented in this way in Fig. 8 and predict a true value of Young's modulus at $1/L = 0$ of about 200 ± 10 GPa. This is considerably higher than the value of 142 GPa given by the supplier. Both this value and the supplier's strength value are consistent with a test length of 10 mm.

In Fig. 8 are included values of E' corrected for the load-cell extension of 0.001 mm per g. The correction is relatively small and it is to be concluded that a larger proportion of the error in E' results from strain in the fibre mounting adhesive.

Fig. 8. Apparent Young's modulus of fibres plotted as function of sample length on reciprocal scales.

All the above tests were carried out on untreated fibres. On treating a sample of fibres in a 70% solution of hydrofluoric acid it was found that the apparent modulus of a 50 mm sample increased to 180 GPa. A probable explanation of this is a considerable improvement in the adhesion of the fibre ends due to dissolution of the surface oxide.

SEM-examination

The fibre surfaces were relatively smooth but were covered with a large number of shallow irregularities (Fig. 9). An examination of several millimeters on eight fibres revealed a few slightly larger faults such as protuberances and fissures (e.g. Fig. 10). A number of tensile fracture surfaces were examined but these did not reveal any obvious flaws in the bulk of the fibre. Fig. 11 shows a typical fracture while Fig. 12 shows a fracture that occurred at an unusually large protuberance. The latter occurred on a fibre with a 75 mm test length at a relatively low stress of 1600 MPa.

DISCUSSION

The strength behaviour of the SiC fibres is described relatively well by Weibull statistics. However, the modulus of $m = 7.8$ of the dependence of mean strength on fibre length (Eq. (4)) is somewhat higher than the value indicated by the strength variation within samples of constant length. One reason for this could be the difficulty experienced in sampling long fibres. Weaker specimens of the longer samples may never be sampled due to failure before mounting. This would lead to a bias towards higher values of $\bar{\sigma}$.

A probably more important effect is that for the present fibres the assumption of constant diameter is clearly not true (see Fig. 1). This means that, within a sample of given length, the specimen surface area and specimen volume vary, thus causing a wider variation of strengths and consequently a lower value of m than the true value. A plot of $\ln \ln (1/P_S)$ vs $\ln \sigma$ can no longer provide the basis for the determination of the true value of m since the value of V in eq. (2) is not constant. Putting $V = \pi R^2 L$ (R = fibre radius) eq. (2) can be written:

$$\ln \ln (1/P_S) - 2 \ln R = \ln L + m \ln \sigma + \text{const.} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 9. Typical surface of the fibres.

Fig. 10. Larger defect in fig. 9 magnified.

Fig. 11. Typical tensile fracture surface.

Fig. 12. Fracture at large surface defect.

Similarly if the defects are confined to the surface

$$\ln \ln (1/P_G) - \ln R = \ln L + m \ln \sigma + \text{const.} \quad (6)$$

Thus plots of the left hand side of these equations vs. $\ln \sigma$ should yield the correct value of m in the two cases. Taking account of the variation of fibre diameter in this way for the present fibres does indeed lead to an increase in m in most samples. The values approach the value of 7.8 more closely using eq. (5) than eq. (6). This could be interpreted tentatively as evidence that flaws exist throughout the bulk of the fibre rather than being confined to the surface. However, such an interpretation is valid only if the flaw distribution can be assumed independent of fibre diameter. For example, the observed sensitivity to fibre diameter could also result from surface flaws if the surface flaw density were to increase with fibre diameter, for example, as a result of production variables.

The examination of the fibres with SEM, though of limited extent, was sufficient to indicate that surface defects existed on the fibres and were responsible for at least some of the fibre failures.

The strength and Young's modulus of the fibres make them attractive as a reinforcement in composites particularly in view of their oxidation resistance and retention of properties at elevated temperatures. The sensitivity of fibre strength to heat-treatment above 1000°C observed in this study could be a result of surface attack by the hydrogen atmosphere used. Yajima has found that 2 h heat-treatments of the precursor fibre in vacuum caused weakening of the resulting SiC fibre only above 1200°C [4]. Similarly, SiC fibres held for 30 min. at temperature in vacuum prior to testing, exhibited no significant reduction in the at-temperature fibre strength up to 1400°C [4].

CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical strength behaviour of multifilament SiC fibres can be described satisfactorily using Weibull statistics although the interpretation is complicated somewhat by the relatively wide distribution of fibre diameter.

The mean strength of fibre samples could be expressed by the empirical equation:

$$\ln \bar{\sigma} = 8.12 - 0.128 \ln L$$

where L is the sample fibre length in mm and $\bar{\sigma}$ the strength in N/mm².

The Young's modulus of the fibres was determined as 200 ±10 GPa.

Heat treatments of the fibres above 1000°C in hydrogen caused a reduction of the Weibull modulus and a decrease in strength.

The initiation of at least some of the fibre failures could be attributed to defects on the fibre surface.

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